

SPECIFIC QUALITY OF PRODUCT COMPETITIVENESS PARAMETERS

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Abstract: Product quality is one of the most important indicators of the activity of enterprises and organizations. Product quality improvement to a certain extent determines the survival of enterprises and organizations in market conditions, the pace of scientific and technical development, the growth of production efficiency, and the economy of all types of resources used in enterprises and organizations. According to the international standard ISO 9000, "quality" is a set of properties and characteristics of the product, which are the fulfillment of the needs defined for the product. The international standard quality can be defined as a set of specific properties, form, appearance, and conditions of use given to the product so that it is suitable for the purposes for which it is intended.

Keywords: product, quality, standard, competition, system, standardization, metrology, quality system, regulatory document, quality management, regulation, quality indicators.

Competitiveness is the ability to withstand competition, to be able to resist it. In this case, "competitiveness" is applied to goods and enterprises, firms, and other organizations [1].

Firstly, the competitiveness of the manufacturer is its ability to maintain and expand sales markets due to its specific goal-oriented activities, both in terms of product quality characteristics and other manufacturers-competitors. All solutions

related to entering new sales markets, restructuring the organizational structure, modifying and mastering new types of products, changing production volumes, replacing the main production funds, and changing business relations and marketing policy are subordinated to ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise [2]. While the categories of product and enterprise competitiveness are interrelated, the important differences are that product competitiveness is evaluated and researched in the time interval corresponding to the life cycle of the product, and enterprise competitiveness research is based on a much longer period that corresponds to the period in which the enterprise operates [3]. the competitiveness of the product is considered concerning each of its types, and the competitiveness of the enterprise covers all the variable nomenclature of the produced product and its production technical potential, the level of competitiveness of the enterprise is analyzed by itself, and the evaluation of the competitiveness of the goods is the exclusive right of the consumer [4]. According to its structure, the competitiveness of the enterprise is much more complicated than the competitiveness of the product, because its object is the entire production economic activity of the enterprise [5].

Secondly, the competitiveness of a product is its relative description, which reflects the differences between this product from competing products, firstly, in terms of its suitability for one social need, and secondly, in terms of the costs of satisfying this need [6]. Product competitiveness is characterized by three groups of indicators: utility, and consumer costs for satisfying the consumer's needs with this product. Product competitiveness parameters (Fig. 1) are normative (goods' compliance with standards, technical conditions, legislation), technical (technological properties that determine the product's field of application, reliability, long-term service, power, etc.), economic (consumer's purchase of goods, is divided into such parameters as the level of operating and disposal costs, that is, the consumer price) and organizational [7].

Competitive parameters

Normative				technical				economic				organizational			
International requirements	State requirements	Regional requirements	Ist e breeder requirements	Marked	Ergonomic	Constructive and technical parameter	Esthetic	Product price	Shipping costs	Employee training	Others	discounts	Delivery	Delivery	Warranty conditions and others

Figure 1 shows the competitiveness parameters of the product.

Product quality is the most important indicator of enterprise activity. Product quality improvement to a certain extent determines the survival of the enterprise in the market conditions, the rate of scientific and technical development, the growth of production efficiency, and the economy of all types of resources used in the enterprise. There are quite a lot of clear-economic interpretations of the concept of quality [8]. According to the international standard ISO 9000:2000, "quality" is a set of properties and characteristics of a product that give the product its ability to meet specified or expected needs [9].

The international standard defines quality as a set of specific properties, form, appearance, and conditions of use given to the product for it to be suitable for the purposes for which it is intended. Each of these elements is determined by quality requirements, these requirements are reflected in the product's technical specifications, construction documents, and technical conditions at the design stage, and include the quality of raw materials, structural dimensions, color uniformity, gloss, etc [10].

The essence of product quality is ГОСТ 15467 "Product quality management. Basic concepts. According to the terms and tariffs, quality is understood as a set of product properties, which ensure that the product is suitable for meeting certain needs by the purposes for which it is intended [11]. According to the ISO 8402 standard interpretation of the International Organization for Standardization, quality is a set of properties and

characteristics of products or services that give these products or services the ability to meet the needs that they are supposed to meet or are expected to meet [12].

To more fully describe the essence of product quality, it is necessary to define the concepts of the technical level of the product, the quality ring, quality indicators, and the competitiveness of the product comparing the values of the indicators describing the technical perfection of the evaluated product with the values of the corresponding basic indicators. The technical level of the product is a component of product quality, reflected in various indicators and increased as a result of the use of original design solutions, the use of new materials, the introduction of advanced technological processes of production, and quality control of manufactured products [13].

The quality ring is the life cycle of the product, which includes the following stages that implement quality management: marketing, market research, and study, design, and development of technical requirements, product development, material and technical support, preparation and development of production processes, control, testing and acceptance, placement and storage, product distribution and sale, assembly and operation, technical and warranty service, disposal [14].

Quality indicators are an interrelated set of product indicators, which describe its intended purpose, reliability, technology, level of standardization and unification, aesthetic, ergonomic, ecological properties, patent-legal aspects, transportability, safety, and economic parameters.

Product competitiveness - the product's ability to be more attractive for consumption compared to other products of the same type and intended for similar purposes, due to the high degree of conformity of the product's quality and value characteristics with the requirements of this market and consumer values [15].

At the international level, quality requirements are defined by the 9000 series ISO standards. The first edition of these standards was adopted at the end of the 80s of the 20th century and marked a new level of international standardization. The standards penetrated directly into the production processes, and in the management area, specific requirements were set for the quality assurance systems. They founded the beginning of quality system

certification - shi. An independent direction of management - quality management appeared. Today, scholars and practitioners are linking modern methods of quality management with total quality management methodology [16]. ISO 9000 standards set a uniform international approach to contractual conditions for the assessment of quality systems and at the same time regulated the relationship between product manufacturers and consumers. In other words, ISO standards are focused only on satisfying the interests of the consumer while strictly adhering to the production culture [17].

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